

From Field to Chain: A Blockchain-based Automatic Insurance Framework for Smart Agriculture

Ivan Zyrianoff^{**†}, Lorenzo Gigli^{*}, Marco Di Felice^{*†}, Vasilios A. Siris[‡], Thanasis G. Papaioannou[§], Federico Montori^{*†}

^{*}Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Bologna, Italy

[†]Advanced Research Center on Electronic Systems, University of Bologna, Italy

[‡] Athens Univ. of Economics & Business, Athens, Greece

[§] Dept. of Digital Industry Technologies, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Greece

Abstract—The agricultural landscape is vulnerable to numerous risks caused by adverse weather conditions that can provoke significant damage. Traditional insurance systems often cause disputed over claims, resulting into cumbersome and ambiguous procedures, and, sometimes, in unfair conclusions. Internet of Things (IoT) and blockchain technologies come as a potential enabler for smart insurance systems, which release reimbursements on top of an on-chain smart contract and verifiable and tamper-proof IoT data evidence. In this paper, we propose a smart insurance system based on blockchain technologies in which an oracle network is devoted to collect – and agree upon – IoT data coming from heterogeneous sources with different owners. We test our system on a real deployment of weather stations in medicinal herb plantations located in northern Italy. We then simulate potential attacks and demonstrate the resilience of the system in producing truthful results.

Index Terms—Blockchain, IoT, smart agriculture, smart insurance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The agricultural sector, a cornerstone of global economies, is inherently vulnerable to a multitude of risks, from adverse weather conditions and pest outbreaks to market volatility. Climate change is exacerbating natural disasters and extreme weather phenomena, leading agricultural companies and farmers to increasingly worry about the future conditions of their land [1]. Traditional agricultural insurance models, while providing a safety net, often present challenges such as information asymmetry, high administrative costs, and disputes over claim assessment. These inefficiencies can lead to a lack of trust between insurers and insured parties, hindering the widespread adoption and effectiveness of vital risk management tools.

In an era defined by rapid technological advancement, the integration of Internet of Things (IoT) devices and blockchain technology presents a transformative opportunity for agricultural insurance. By capturing critical agricultural parameters – such as soil moisture, temperature, humidity, and crop health – directly from the field, IoT sensors provide an unprecedented level of granularity and accuracy in risk assessment. IoT technology has long been used for precision agriculture and

monitoring [2] [3]. This paper delves into the concept of "smart insurance" for agricultural scenarios, proposing a novel framework that leverages real-time, *trustworthy* IoT data.

These systems integrate IoT data collected from the field onto a secure, immutable blockchain. This distributed ledger technology ensures the integrity, transparency, and immutability of all recorded data, from environmental conditions to crop yields. By creating an auditable and tamper-proof record, blockchain technologies eliminate the need for intermediaries in data verification, significantly reducing fraudulent claims and enhancing operational efficiency. This convergence of IoT data and blockchain not only streamlines the claims process but, more importantly, fosters an environment of enhanced trustworthiness and transparency between agricultural insurers and their clients, paving the way for more equitable, responsive, and resilient insurance solutions.

This approach has recently gained traction in the research landscape. For example, [4] proposed a blockchain-based approach for crop index-based insurance in agricultural supply chains, demonstrating automated insurance payouts based on predefined weather and crop yield parameters. Their work mainly focuses on automating smart contracts and delegates the oracle (an oracle is an off-chain node that connects the deterministic blockchain with external *non-deterministic* information) solution for retrieving IoT data to external solutions like Chainlink. In [5], the authors demonstrate how Hyperledger Fabric can address critical issues in agriculture by developing a multi-channel network infrastructure that leverages its secure and scalable features to satisfy different agricultural needs, including data sharing, machinery service coordination, and insurance claim processing. The work in [6] proposes the AgriSSIOracle framework, a trusted IoT data-sharing system that utilizes blockchain-based Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) and decentralized oracles to enhance data trustworthiness and security for agricultural insurance.

Current solutions present limitations, their focus on automating smart contracts, delegating the oracle solution for retrieving IoT data to external solutions (e.g., Chainlink). Furthermore, they do not take into account the potential mali-

cious behavior of data sources (sensor) nor their tamperability, while we put our focus on the heterogeneity of the ownership of data sources to mitigate this issue. In this paper, we propose a blockchain-based smart insurance system tailored to agricultural scenarios that follows the trend of global IoT data markets [7]. In our system, insured parties, such as farmers, can periodically trigger IoT sensor data requests generated by the insurance contract, which is translated into a smart contract. These requests are handled through a set of dedicated smart contracts and resolved by an oracle network, in which data oracles cooperate to converge to a single truthful result by querying data sources belonging to different parties to ensure fairness. Data sources and oracles are also picked randomly to avoid collusion attacks.

In detail, we make the following contributions:

- We design the architecture of our proposed blockchain-based smart insurance system and its workflow.
- We set up a test case using real weather stations that we deployed on-field as part of a funded project.
- We quantitatively assess the system’s robustness against a suite of emulated attacks grounded in the real-world data traces, measuring its ability to prevent erroneous insurance payouts.

The paper is structured as follows: Section II describes the architecture and the workflow of the system, Section III explains how we deployed the sensors and collected the data, Section IV presents our evaluation of the system against possible attacks, finally V concludes the paper.

II. ARCHITECTURE & IMPLEMENTATION

In this Section, we illustrate the software architecture and implementation details of the entire system, along with the interactions among the software components and the actors involved, as shown in Fig. 1. Our smart insurance mechanism is handled by a dedicated smart contract stipulated by both parties: the insurer (i.e., the insurance company) and the insured (i.e., the farmer). The smart insurance contract, when issued, triggers a coin stake on both parties: the insured pays the insurer, while the insurer locks a certain amount of money on the chain until the contract ends. The release of the insurance prize to the insured occurs upon the occurrence

of a specific event, typically a set of thresholds that must be exceeded by sensor values of various types. This may need to occur consecutively a certain number of times over a sufficiently large period, and the geographic area of the sensor data request must exactly match the area reported in the insurance contract. This concept follows existing index-based approaches.

Upon the occurrence of an adverse weather event, the insured can then issue an IoT data request from the field. Our data request system is heavily based on our past contribution, namely ZONIA [8]. The system revolves around several smart contracts deployed on an EVM-based blockchain. The smart contracts are a simplified version of the ones found in ZONIA [8], the technical details of which are outside the scope of this paper. The system is then supported by a number of data oracles and off-chain entities that subscribe to our system and run our Oracle software to interact with the system. Data oracles must stake a certain amount of currency to participate in the system, as they will be eligible for compensation for each successfully resolved request, as well as to deter potential Sybil attacks. In our system, the insured can request sensor data via their insurance contract by committing a certain amount of money and identifying a geographical area of interest that matches the one specified in the insurance contract. A subset of the oracles receives the request. It queries a predefined set of sensors in the geographic area to obtain their sensor data corresponding to the type specified in the request. Sensors subscribed to our system have an actual account on the blockchain and are referred to as "producers." Subsequently, the selected oracles reach a consensus by aggregating the responses of the producers and posting the final answer to the request on the blockchain. Figure 1 provides a more detailed overview of the steps that form a request resolution process. Let us walk the interested reader through the five steps that compose this process.

1: An insured party submits a data request to the blockchain through the related insurance contract by committing a certain amount of money. The request contains the type of data to be fetched (e.g. temperature, humidity, wind speed, rainfall, etc.), the geographical area of interest, the number K_O of oracles to involve, and the number K_P of data producers. A higher K_O ensures a higher quality of the response, hindering collusions. Similarly, a higher K_P ensures that the final response is averaged out from a larger number of sources, effectively canceling out potential malicious ones. All these parameters are defined a priori when redacting the insurance contract. Once the request is composed, it is stored on a special gate contract.

2: Upon submitting the request, all Oracles participate in generating a universal seed value, which is essential for reliably generating random numbers on a distributed ledger. This is done by running Verifiable Random Functions (VRF) [9] as explained in detail in [8]. Oracles then randomly select a subset of them, with cardinality K_O . By using the same seed they all deterministically obtain the same subset, which is called “oracle committee”. The oracle committee then picks

Fig. 1: TRACE architecture with the three subsystems.

up the actual request from the gate contract.

3: As soon as the request is posted, all producers in the area that respond to the query signal their intention to be selected. The gate contract leaves a time window for producers to subscribe to the query by adding themselves to an on-chain array. The oracle committee then uses the same seed previously computed via the VRF to randomly select a subset of producers who subscribed to the query, with cardinality K_P . Once they are selected, all oracles in the committee query all selected producers and post on-chain the hash of the responses using a commit-reveal scheme – so that committed values cannot be changed later.

4: When all hashes are submitted, oracles finally post the responses they obtained on-chain. At this point, there are $K_O \times K_P$ datapoints written on the smart contract. The oracle committee engages in a deterministic procedure called “truth inference”, in which a single value is extracted from all responses and deemed truthful. Our system does not define a single truth inference function, which can be any function that takes a set of values as input and outputs a single value as output. Simple aggregation functions like the mean or the median are good candidates; however, the more information we have about the sources, the more we can apply complex truth discovery procedures to obtain weights for the aggregation [10]. In our implementation, we used the median because it is resilient against outliers that would otherwise indefinitely deviate from other aggregation functions such as the mean [11].

5: The output of the truth inference procedure is written on the blockchain by the quickest oracle since the result is verifiable by any blockchain node. The user obtains the value and releases the payment, which gets distributed among the oracle committee and the K_P producers, weighted by how much their response is close to the inferred truth – *i.e.*, malicious or imprecise producers will get a lower, if not null, reward.

This basic architecture ensures fairness; in fact, oracles and producers are selected randomly to mitigate Sybil attacks. Producers, in particular, may belong to any of the actors: in Figure 1, they may belong to the farmer, the insurance company, or any third party. Choosing a heterogeneous set of producers is the key to ensuring that no one is interested in behaving maliciously. Note that adding mechanisms based on reputation, as we did in [8], has been proven to increase resilience against malicious actors significantly. These, while necessary, are outside the scope of this paper, and we redirect interested readers to dedicated papers.

III. DATA COLLECTION

To ground our analysis in a realistic setting, we utilize a real-world dataset collected from weather stations deployed in precision agricultural fields focused on Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (MAPs). Our work leverages data from eight Milesight WTS506¹ weather stations, each installed on a different farm,

¹<https://www.milesight.com/iot/product/lorawan-sensor/wts506>

Fig. 2: In-situ deployment of the weather station positioned within a medicinal plant cultivation field.

Fig. 3: Geographic distribution of the deployed sensor network. Red markers indicate weather station locations, and blue markers represent LoRaWAN Gateways. The yellow line provides a 3 km scale reference.

with data collection commencing on March 27, 2025. Each station is configured to transmit a new data packet via LoRaWAN [12] every five minutes, ensuring a consistent and timely stream of information. Figure 6 shows an on-site deployment of a station, while Figure 3 presents their geographic distribution across the eight farms. The WTS506 sensor suite captures the following environmental parameters: temperature ($\pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$), relative humidity ($\pm 2\%$ RH), barometric pressure (± 0.02 hPa), wind speed (± 0.3 m/s), wind direction ($\pm 3^\circ$), and rainfall ($\pm 5\%$). For this analysis, we focus specifically on temperature values, although the proposed framework can be straightforwardly extended to other measured parameters or a combination thereof.

Fig. 4: Attack success rate (i.e., trigger wrongful payment) in agricultural smart insurance

IV. EXPERIMENTS

This section evaluates the performance of the proposed oracle architecture (detailed in Section II) within an agricultural smart insurance context. We consider a scenario involving a smart insurance contract between a farmer and an insurance company. In the evaluated scenario, the insurance protects farmers against crop damage due to exceptionally high temperatures (above 50°C), with a payout triggered if this threshold is exceeded for five consecutive queries. The weather stations, as presented in Section III, function as data producers. The experiments utilize real-world data traces from these weather stations, and each producer, when queried, provides the most recent sensor reading recorded at or before the query timestamp. In both evaluated scenarios, a subset of the data producers (representing compromised farmer-owned weather stations) collude to tamper with their reported data, submitting artificially high values to simulate conditions that would wrongfully trigger an insurance payout. The compromised sensors report values synthetically generated around 80°C – expecting to shift the derived truth reading in case of distance-based calculations (e.g., the average). The attack is initiated at a randomly selected timestamp, following an initial period allowing for reputation establishment. The attack persists for a duration of 4 hours, after which the compromised producers revert to reporting truthfully. To assess the impact of attacker dominance, the number of colluding producers was varied from 1 to 6, out of a total of 8 initially deployed physical weather station producers.

A key feature of our architecture is the decoupling of clients from direct producer selection. This mechanism, involving reputation-weighted random selection, aims to distribute queries across diverse producers, thereby enhancing resilience against targeted attacks. To model the presence of third-party data providers (e.g., a neighboring farm monetizing its weather station data), we introduced *virtual data sources*. Each virtual source is assigned a set of 3 unique, existing weather station trace files. When queried, a virtual source retrieves the latest valid data point (as per the data generation and freshness logic) from each of its assigned underlying traces and returns the average of these values. We evaluated scenarios with varying numbers of these honest, third-party virtual sources: (i) 0 Virtual Sources: All producers are the initially deployed physical stations. (ii) 2, 4, and 6 Virtual Sources: These configurations add 2, 4, or 6 honest virtual

sources, respectively, to the set of producers, increasing the total producer pool and the proportion of honest participants.

To benchmark our system, we compare its performance against two baseline aggregation strategies, inspired by existing IoT oracle concepts:

- *Avg Baseline*: This represents a simple oracle that queries a selected set of known producers and computes the arithmetic mean of their reported values. This is characteristic of basic aggregation in systems like DiOr-SGX [13].
- *Median Baseline*: Similar to the Avg Baseline, but employs the median for aggregation, known for its robustness to outliers.

For our proposed system, we employed a weighted median as the Truth Inference algorithm. The weights are derived from a dynamically updated reputation score for each participating producer. Reputation scores are adjusted after each query cycle based on producer performance relative to the inferred truth and internal consistency, details on the score update are on Gigli et al. [8]. For each simulation configuration, we conducted 30 independent repetitions. The results in Fig. 4 showcase the robustness of our approach, specially when considering 3rd-party sources. Our approach, even with no third-party producers, demonstrates significantly better resilience in scenarios up to 50% of malicious sources (i.e., four attackers), due to its reputation system and randomized selection. However, when the number of attackers surpasses the 50% threshold (5 attackers or more), all methods that do not employ the decoupling converge to total failure. The inclusion of honest third-party producers clearly demonstrates our architecture’s strength. With only two 3rd-party producers, we achieve a low attack success rate even with five malicious nodes. Further, configurations with four and six 3rd party sensors demonstrated to be robust against attacks even when almost all of the farmer’s sources are compromised.

To analyze the internal dynamics of our architecture, we examine the evolution of source reputations over time in scenarios without attackers (Fig. 5) and with four attackers (Fig. 6). Each figure’s left panel illustrates the reputation scores, bounded between -1.0 and 1.0, while the right panel displays the corresponding temperature values reported by each weather station. In the non-attack scenario, reputation scores fluctuate due to benign causes as sensor malfunctions (e.g., reporting 0°C) or persistent physical biases from sensor placement. In the attack scenario, there is a sharp decline in the malicious sources’ reputations during the attack period. The swift degradation is the result of the reputation update after each query, which avoids *milking attacks* by exploiting a high reputation with a damaging submission before the system reacts. The reputational penalty leads to their de-prioritization in the randomized source selection process, thereby minimizing their impact on system-wide truth inference. Moreover, if a kick-out mechanism were implemented (e.g., removing sources with reputations below -0.4), these malicious nodes would be swiftly expelled from the system, mitigating immediate damage and preventing future contributions.

Fig. 5: Weather station reputation (left) and read temperature values (right) across time without an attack

Fig. 6: Weather station reputation (left) and read temperature values (right) across time with a collusion attack (four attackers)

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented an index-based, blockchain-based smart insurance system specifically tailored for agricultural scenarios. The system relies on a network of data oracles that need to agree upon the data extracted from the data sources. The commit-reveal scheme ensures that they cannot know a priori the data obtained by the others so they cannot directly collude. We proved the efficiency of the system using data coming from a weather station deployment under our control in a real setting and simulated attacks conducted by malicious actors. The system has proven its resilience to even a high number of attackers, especially if complying with a reputation scheme. Future works are oriented to study reputation schemes to make the system even more solid.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper was produced under the ZONIA-MC project. ZONIA-MC has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme through the NGI TRUSTCHAIN programme under cascade funding agreement No. 101093274. This paper is also supported by the TRACE (Innovazione e tracciabilità nella filiera produttiva di piante ad interesse officinale coltivate nell'areale emiliano-romagnolo) project, CoPSR 2023-2027 Emilia-Romagna – Intervento SRG01.

REFERENCES

[1] L. Cremonini, P. Randi, M. Fazzini, M. Nardino, F. Rossi, and T. Georgiadis, "Causes and impacts of flood events in emilia-romagna (italy) in may 2023," *Land*, vol. 13, no. 11, p. 1800, 2024.

[2] I. Zyrianoff, A. Heideker, D. Silva, and C. Kamienski, "Scalability of an internet of things platform for smart water management for agriculture," in *2018 23rd conference of open innovations association (FRUCT)*, pp. 432–439, IEEE, 2018.

[3] L. Colizzi, D. Caivano, C. Ardito, G. Desolda, A. Castrignanò, M. Matera, R. Khosla, D. Moshou, K.-M. Hou, F. Pinet, *et al.*, "Introduction to agricultural iot," in *Agricultural Internet of Things and Decision Support for Precision Smart Farming*, pp. 1–33, Elsevier, 2020.

[4] I. A. Omar, R. Jayaraman, K. Salah, H. R. Hasan, J. Antony, and M. Omar, "Blockchain-based approach for crop index insurance in agricultural supply chain," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 118660–118675, 2023.

[5] Z. Hu, B. Kim, and J. Jeong, "A study on mechanization, data, and insurance challenges for agriculture based on hyperledger fabric," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 144855–144869, 2024.

[6] M. T. K. Makkithaya, and N. V.G., "A trusted iot data sharing and secure oracle based access for agricultural production risk management," *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, vol. 204, p. 107544, 2023.

[7] L. Gigli, I. Zyrianoff, F. Montori, C. Aguzzi, L. Roffia, and M. Di Felice, "A decentralized oracle architecture for a blockchain-based iot global market," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 8, pp. 86–92, 2023.

[8] L. Gigli, I. Zyrianoff, F. Montori, L. Sciuillo, C. Kamienski, and M. Di Felice, "Zonia: a zero-trust oracle system for blockchain iot applications," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.10532*, 2024.

[9] S. Micali, M. Rabin, and S. Vadhan, "Verifiable random functions," in *40th annual symposium on foundations of computer science (cat. No. 99CB37039)*, pp. 120–130, IEEE, 1999.

[10] Y. Li, J. Gao, C. Meng, Q. Li, L. Su, B. Zhao, W. Fan, and J. Han, "A survey on truth discovery," *ACM Sigkdd Explorations Newsletter*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 1–16, 2016.

[11] B. Zhao and J. Han, "A probabilistic model for estimating real-valued truth from conflicting sources," *Proc. of QDB*, vol. 1817, 2012.

[12] A. Pagano, D. Croce, I. Tinnirello, and G. Vitale, "A survey on iora for smart agriculture: Current trends and future perspectives," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 3664–3679, 2023.

[13] S. Woo, J. Song, and S. Park, "A distributed oracle using intel sgx for blockchain-based iot applications," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 9, 2020.